

Polarographic Studies on Composition and Stabilities of Complexes of Some Tetracyclines with $UO_2(II)$ in Aqueous Medium

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The composition and stability of complexes of tetracycline, oxytetracycline, chlorotetracycline and demethyl-chlorotetracycline with $UO_2(II)$ have been determined and discussed.

EXTENSIVE polarographic studies have been carried out on the electrode reactions of $UO_2(II)$ ion in aqueous and aquo-non-aqueous media containing non-complexing, weak complexing and strong complexing agents¹⁻⁵. One, two or three polarographic waves were reported depending on the acidity of the medium, the nature of supporting and complexing agents, and the choice of the system. Literature reveals that the complex formation of $UO_2(II)$ ion with tetracycline (TC) was studied by Mahgoub *et al*⁶ only, using conductometric and spectrophotometric (visible, uv and ir) techniques. An 1:1 complex was reported, the stability of which was found to be 1.02×10^6 . The structure of this complex, as reported by these authors is shown in Fig. 1. There is no report on the complexation of $UO_2(II)$ with oxytetracycline (OTC), chlorotetracycline (CTC) and demethylchlorotetracycline (DMCTC). In an effort to bring a perspective to this field, we have undertaken these studies on the $UO_2(II)$ -TC, -OTC, -CTC and -DMCTC systems in aqueous medium.

Fig. 1. Structure of $UO_2(II)$ -TC complex due to Mahgoub *et al*.

The scope of this work was restricted to an elucidation of the complexation behaviour of $UO_2(II)$ with tetracyclines, in view of the fact that the reduction of the antibiotics starts at about -0.75 V in the pH range 1.5-2.0. Only a few polaro-

grams were taken to understand the complexation of $UO_2(I)$ with TC.

Experimental

All polarographic waves were recorded with a manual polarograph⁷ using a capillary with a mercury height (corrected) of 42.28 cm, and a drop-time of 5.56 s, which corresponds to a mercury flow of 2.42 mg s^{-1} in 0.1 M NaClO_4 at 0.18 V.

All systems were studied at three pH values (about 1.55, 1.74 and 1.96) in (i) absence and (ii) presence of a constant amount of $UO_2(II)$ (1.90×10^{-4} – $1.14 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$). The pH of the solutions was maintained between 1.5 and 2.0, since below pH 1.5 disproportionation⁸ occurs appreciably and above pH 2.1 precipitation occurs in the $UO_2(II)$ -antibiotic systems.

Since the reduction of the $UO_2(II)$ ion occurs in successive steps, a $UO_2(II)$ complex is reduced to a lower valency state from a higher valency state, and the process may, therefore, be represented as follows :

where n and m are the valencies of the metal ion in the oxidised and reduced states, p and q are the corresponding coordination numbers of the two states and X is the ligand. The complexed species $UO_2(II)$ and $UO_2(I)$ differ by only one electron. Thus, in order to determine the characteristics of the possible complexed species in solution, it may readily be shown that the shift in half-wave potential for the above system (with the assumption that the diffusion coefficient of MX_p and MX_q are approximately equal) with increasing antibiotic concentra-

tion is given by :

$$\Delta E_{1/2} = E_{1/2}(M)UO_2(II) - E_{1/2}(C)UO_2(II) \\ = (p-q) \frac{RT}{F} \ln[X] - \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{\beta_{UO_2(II)}}{\beta_{UO_2(II)}} \dots (ii)$$

This equation suggests that a plot of $E_{1/2}$ against $-\log [X]$ may provide a knowledge of the difference in the number of ligand molecules bound in the oxidised and reduced forms, and also that the value of each one of the stability constants cannot be determined for this system (i.e. that only the ratio of stability constants can be calculated). These values have been calculated by the method of DeFord and Hume⁹ as improved by Irving¹⁰.

Results and Discussion

The results of polarographic reduction of $UO_2(II)$ in perchlorate medium show that the reciprocal slope of the straight lines, obtained by plotting E_{de} vs $\log [i/(i_a - i)]$ of the first wave was 60 ± 1 mV, which is in excellent agreement with the theoretical value of 59 mV for a one-electron reversible reduction. The half-wave potential of this wave was found to be -178 mV and is independent of the pH of the solution and the height (corrected) of the mercury column. The second step of this system seems to comprise two waves both with very nearly the same half-wave potential since a break in the log plots

In the presence of increasing amount of TC, OTC, CTC and DMCTC, the half-wave potential of the first wave of $UO_2(II)$ ion (at $1.5 < pH < 2.0$) gets shifted towards cathodic potential indicating formation of complexed species of the metal ion with the antibiotics. Log plots analyses gave the value of reciprocal slopes as 63 ± 3 mV indicating that all the systems are reversible involving one electron. i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{corr}}$ plots show the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction process ($i_d/\sqrt{h_{corr}} = 0.174 \pm 0.005 \mu A \text{ cm}^{-1/2}$).

The results of the present study show that the reduction of $UO_2(II)$ ion in perchlorate medium produces a three-stepped polarographic wave involving three electrons.

To obtain an idea of the composition and stabilities of $UO_2(II)$ -antibiotic complexes, $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log [LH_2^+]$ and $-\log [LH^+]$ (LH_2^+ being the protonated antibiotic molecule) were plotted for the $UO_2(II)$ -TC system only (curves not shown), leaving the plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log [L^{2-}]$, for the following reasons :

- (i) It has been observed¹¹ that the TC, OTC, CTC and DMCTC molecules coordinate through the O-10 and O-11 with Cd(II), Pb(II) and Cu(II) ions, and pK_a^H of the antibiotics were responsible for the chelation.

Fig. 2. Polarographic wave of $UO_2(II)$ and log plots of its I and II steps (i_a : divis. = $4.69 \times 10^{-2} \mu A$).

was observed (Fig. 2). The ratio of the diffusion current of the second step to the first was found to be 1.99 ± 0.01 . This clearly indicates that twice as many electrons are involved during the second wave as during the first. It also suggests that the disproportionation phenomenon was not so effective as to produce any difficulty in the study of the metal ion complexes. The plot of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{corr}}$ was found to be straight line passing through origin ($i_d/\sqrt{h_{corr}} = 0.179 \pm 0.002 \mu A \text{ cm}^{-1/2}$) indicating the diffusion-controlled nature of the reduction processes.

- (ii) In acidic medium, nitrogen at the C-4 does not take part in coordination¹²⁻¹⁹ because of the strong repulsion between the solvated OH-12a and protonated dimethylamine group.
- (iii) Mahgoub *et al*⁸ have proposed the coordination sites for TC as the oxygen atoms at C-1 and C-2.

These plots were smooth curves indicating the possibilities of successive complexation in the

$\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC system. The stability constants were, therefore, calculated by the method of DeFord and Hume⁹ as improved by Irving¹⁰. An observation obtained here was that the plots of $F_0[\text{LH}_2]/F_1[\text{LH}^-]$ and $F_1[\text{LH}_2]/F_1[\text{LH}^-]$ vs $[\text{LH}_2]/[\text{LH}^-]$ were straight lines, the latter being parallel to the $[\text{LH}_2]/[\text{LH}^-]$ axis, due to the formation of only one complexed species with 1 : 1 metal to ligand ratio. The values of ratio of stability constants, $\beta_{\text{MX}_p}/\beta_{\text{MX}_q}$, so obtained for the possible complex species were 3.55×10^4 and 1.95×10^9 , respectively using pK_1^H and pK_2^H . The reported value of the stability constant of the 1 : 1 complex of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ with TC⁹ was 1.02×10^6 , which is higher than ours for $\beta_{\text{MX}_p}/\beta_{\text{MX}_q}$ when calculated with the assumption that pK_1^H is involved in coordination, and is much less than that when calculated using pK_2^H . The limiting values of $\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta \log [\text{LH}_2]$ and $\Delta E_{1/2}/\Delta \log [\text{LH}^-]$ were found to be the same i.e., about -0.056 , indicating that $(p-q)$ for the ligand is 1. Thus, one more TC molecule (whatever be the form) is attached to the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ complex than to that of $\text{UO}_2(\text{I})$.

A comparison between the wave of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ (0.3 mM) alone ($E_{1/4} - E_{3/4} = 67$ mV, $-E_{1/2} = 874$ mV) and that obtained by the difference in i at various potentials for the waves of TC (0.3 mM) in presence and in absence of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ($E_{1/4} - E_{3/4} = 60$ mV, $-E_{1/2} = 874$ mV) under similar conditions of ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$ M), temperature ($30 \pm 0.5^\circ$) and pH (1.98) shows that no appreciable difference occurs in the nature of such waves (Fig. 3). However, the

Fig. 3. Polarograms of TC (0.3 mM) in absence and in presence of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ (0.03 mM) at pH 1.96. (1 div. = 4.69×10^{-9} μA).

log plots of both the waves (obtained by either way) are not identical in shape, the former gives a straight line with a break while the latter a straight line ($-E_{1/2} = 876$ mV, reciprocal slope = 65 mV). It can be concluded that the second step of reduction wave of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ in absence of TC is the resultant of two different reduction processes having approximately equal half-wave potential and involves two electrons. But the same step of the wave of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ in presence of TC shows the presence of only one reduction process involving two electrons. We may, therefore, consider that the value of q is practically zero and that of p is 1. In other words, the complex formed by the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ion with TC has the composition of 1 : 1 with respect to metal ion and the ligand. The values of stability constants of this complex were $\log \beta_1 = 4.55$ or 8.29 when calculated using pK_1^H and pK_2^H , respectively. To get an idea of the correct value of $\log \beta_1$ for the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC complex, and consequently to know the complexing species for this system as LH_2 or LH^- , we consider the order of stabilities of Cu(II) and $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ complexes with the same ligand.

The stabilities of complexes of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ion are generally found to be of the same order as those of the Cu(II)^{20,21} with the same ligand. In certain cases, the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ion is reported to form stronger complexes than Cu(II)^{20,21}, while in some systems weaker. As a rule²⁰, $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ ion forms stronger complexes than Cu(II) with oxygen donors, but the order is reversed with oxygen and nitrogen donors. Thus, the value of $\log \beta_1$ for the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC system should not be less than 7.61 i.e. the $\log \beta_1$ value of the Cu(II)-TC system¹¹ as observed under similar experimental conditions. Thus, we may conclude that the value of $\log \beta_1$ for the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC complex must be 8.29 rather than 4.55, and it is only the pK_1^H which is involved in the complexation of the $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC system, rather than pK_2^H , and consequently, the LH^- species of TC may be regarded as ligand for these systems.

An examination of the structure of $\text{UO}_2(\text{II})$ -TC complex as reported by Mahgoub *et al*⁶ shows that an intramolecular change of hydrogen atom takes place from the amide NH_2 to convert the ketonic oxygen into an alcoholic one in contrast with the views of Stezowski^{18,19}. These workers¹⁹ have shown that NH_2 group of the tricarbonylmethane system remains as such, and only the proton of the alcoholic group at C-3 is involved in the protonation of the amide oxygen. This result explains how intramolecular change within the tricarbonylmethane group may take place to give two isomers of TC in solution as shown in Scheme 1. One of the two isomer presented in the scheme may provide the

Scheme 1. Deprotonation of the first proton due to Stephens *et al*.

similar binding as presented by Mahgoub *et al*⁶, i.e., through O-1 and O-2 amide, provided that C-3 hydroxyl group should be dissociated as not considered by these authors. The presence of OH group at C-3 suggests that the complexation of $UO_2(II)$ with TC should be independent of pK_1^H , and consequently the complexing species should not be LH_2 . This provides a support for our conclusion.

Because of similarities in properties of tetracyclines in structure and pK^H values, we assume that the complexation of $UO_2(II)$ with OTC, CTC and DMCTC takes place through the pK^H values of the antibiotics and that the complexing species were LH^- for these systems. The amount of such species was calculated with the help of pK_1^H and the amount of antibiotic and the pH of the solution. The values of β_1 for all systems were calculated by the method of DeFord and Hume⁹ as improved by Irving¹⁰. In all the three systems, i.e., $UO_2(II)$ -OTC, -CTC and -DMCTC, both $F_0[LH^-]$ and $F_1[LH^-]$ when plotted against $[LH^-]$ gave straight lines, the latter being horizontal to the $[LH^-]$ axis indicating the formation of only one complex species with metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1.

Thus, from the plots of $F_0[X]$ vs $[X]$ and above discussion, one may easily conclude that it is not always necessary to infer successive complexation when the plots of $-E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log[X]$ were smooth curves (X being the coordinating species). The obtained values of $\log \beta_1$ for the $UO_2(II)$ -OTC, -CTC and -DMCTC systems are 8.11, 8.06 and 7.96, respectively.

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